

THE PSYCHOLOGY OF SMALL BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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Annotation. *This study explores the role and significance of psychological factors in the management process of small businesses. Special attention is paid to the personal qualities of entrepreneurs, leadership styles, team management skills, psychological strategies in decision-making, and stress management mechanisms. The importance of the socio-psychological environment, motivation systems, and communication skills in the successful operation of small business entities is substantiated. Additionally, psychological challenges that may arise in small businesses and effective ways to manage them are analyzed.*

Keywords: *Small business, entrepreneurial psychology, leadership, motivation, socio-psychological environment, stress management, decision-making, communication skills.*

In a market economy, managers are required to improve their entrepreneurial and business management styles. These management approaches are primarily aimed at achieving specific goals consciously. Throughout this process, adherence to moral values—specifically, entrepreneurial ethics—is essential. The fundamental rules of business ethics include respect for the law, integrity, keeping one's word and contracts, trustworthiness, and social responsibility. Entrepreneurs must never deceive employees, clients, shareholders, executives, suppliers, or regulatory bodies under any circumstances.

In developed countries—particularly Japan and the United States—companies widely apply "ethical codes" for firms and “codes of conduct” for professional business groups. These codes ensure uniform ethical standards within an industry, making it easier to identify unethical behavior among competitors. A core section of any business ethics code pertains to the relationship between entrepreneurs and consumers. The first "Code of Business Conduct" was developed by Americans in 1913 and consisted of seven business principles. These principles were unified under a single concept—that all methods and policies in business should align with the notions of truth and fairness. Over time, the code has undergone several improvements.

In a market economy, the essence of an entrepreneur's management activity is determined by their command of the art of management—such as organizing people into teams, planning, controlling, exchanging information, and skillfully coordinating management processes. An entrepreneur's awareness, initiative, ability to meet people's material and spiritual needs, and their sense of responsibility to their group and society are of great importance. The art of management is fundamental for entrepreneurial leaders—it involves building effective relationships with subordinates and creating a productive organizational environment.

Japan's management style is built on these very principles. The initial social setting in Japan allows for both the social protection and moral development of workers. They utilize psychological insights and well-known traditional methods to train workers in the delicate aspects of tasks and instill discipline. The process of production and quality control are never separated or opposed. In their view, increasing control or the inspector's authority does not guarantee product

quality. Instead, quality should be ensured during the production process by inspecting every completed task. The inspector’s main responsibility is not to punish the worker for defective output but to identify and eliminate the root cause of the issue. Japan has effectively implemented this method, resulting in employees learning self-monitoring and continuously striving for self-improvement. Quality control circles are formed within companies. Similarly, every business leader should aim to apply this method in their workplace. This would help reduce the number of defective products and increase high-quality output without expanding production or hiring additional workers.

The success of an entrepreneur in business largely depends on how well their relationships with partners are established. A partner is someone who participates in a joint activity. Responsible interpersonal relations are critical in strengthening these partnerships—this includes shared ideas and willingness to implement them, strict adherence to contract terms, payment terms, available social benefits (if any), participation in company management, dividend payments at the end of the year, and ensuring a partner receives their share upon leaving.

An entrepreneurial leader’s organizational ability involves forming a cohesive team, influencing both production and educational processes, and guiding the group toward high-level goals. While leading teams in producing material and spiritual values, entrepreneurs must remember that individuals are interconnected and dependent on each other, each with their own needs and goals. Thus, a leader should prioritize interpersonal relationships and human values.

Customer relations are also of critical importance in small businesses. A small business may have various types of customers—brokers, stock exchanges, procurement organizations, processing enterprises, or individuals who regularly order or purchase products. Regardless of whether the client is an organization, firm, or individual, entrepreneurs must remember that they are first and foremost people with specific needs. The entrepreneur’s task is to attract and retain the customer. Every entrepreneur—whether an individual or organization—should dedicate their operations to the customer. To achieve this goal, the following should be ensured:

- Always empathize with the customer’s perspective;
- Avoid unnecessary bureaucracy;
- Maintain post-sale contact with customers.

These are the fundamental components of entrepreneurial psychology.

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